

THE MORPHOLOGY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PBT/LCP BLENDS

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ABSTRACT

Poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) were blended with 10 and 20 wt-% of a thermotropic liquid crystalline polyester (LCP) to prepare "in-situ composites". Morphology and mechanical properties of these blends were investigated. It has been found for the injection molded bars of these blends that LCP forms fine particles and fibrils with less than 1 micron in diameter in the matrix of PBT. The formation of LCP fibrils is closely related to flow conditions during mold filling. Tensile strength and modulus of the blends increase and impact properties decrease with the addition of LCP.

INTRODUCTION

Thermotropic main-chain liquid crystalline polymers (LCPs), when blended with other plastics, may form fibrils in the other plastic during processing because the rigid-rod molecules of LCPs are very easy to align along flow direction. These fibrils act as reinforcement like short fibers for the matrix plastic, and the reinforcements are developed during processing, so polymer blends which contain LCPs are called "in-situ composites". "In-situ composites" have attracted increasing interest because their mechanical properties are comparable to those of glass fiber reinforced thermoplastics, but are more convenient to process and less wear to processing equipment.

Evidently, for "in-situ composite", that is polymer blend containing LCP, the property improvement depends on the formation and distribution of LCP fibrils. And the formation and distribution of LCP fibrils are very sensitive to the processing conditions and to the interaction between LCP and the matrix polymer. A lot of researches have been done on the characterization and analysis of the morphology and properties of these blends[1].

In this paper, blends of a thermotropic LCP, poly(ethylene terephthalate-co-*p*-oxybenzoate) (PET/PHB), with poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) were studied. The morphologies of different shape injection molded specimens and of different parts in the same specimen were investigated. The relationship of mechanical properties with LCP contents in the blends were also investigated and compared with glass fiber reinforced PBT.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.

The LCP used in these experiments was a PET/60PHB type thermotropic copolyester. Both LCP and PBT in this paper were provided by Beijing Institute of Chemical Technology.

Blending and Injection.

PBT was melt blended with 10 and 20 wt-% of LCP by a single screw extruder after being dried at 120°C for 20 hours. The blends were labeled PBT/LCP10/90 and PBT/LCP20/80 respectively. The blend pellets were injection molded into dumbbell and square bars. The dumbbell bars are 101 mm long and 2 mm thick with a 25x6 mm² narrow part, and the square bars are 55x6x4 mm³. The gate is square shaped at one end of the specimen. The metering zone temperature in both the extruder and the injector was 250°C, and the mold temperature in injection molding was about 50°C.

Investigation and Testing.

Apparent viscosity of pure LCP and PBT under different shear rates were measured by a Goettfert Rheograph 2001 rheometer. Morphology of PBT/LCP blends was investigated with a Hitachi S-570 scanning electronic microscope (SEM). The dumbbell and square bars were broken in liquid nitrogen, and the fracture surfaces were observed. Tensile, flexural and Charpy impact properties were tested on a materials testing machine at room temperature, and the specimens were dumbbell and square bars with the above mentioned dimensions respectively. The tensile speed was 10 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. MORPHOLOGY

It has been known that the viscosity ratio of the two components in a blend plays an important part for the morphology development during processing[1,2]. Capillary rheometer was used to measure the apparent viscosities of pure PBT and LCP under the shear rates ranging from 10² to 10⁴ s⁻¹. The rheological curves are shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Viscosity *versus* shear rate for PBT and LCP at 250°C

It can be seen that the apparent viscosities of PBT under these shear rates are one to three times of those of LCP. And this range of shear rate is considered to cover the injecting, mold filling and post-filling speeds. That is, PBT has higher viscosity than LCP during the injection molding, which is considered as a favorable condition for LCP forming fibrils[1].

The characteristic morphology of these PBT/LCP blends is that LCP form fine particles and fibrils with less than 1 micron in diameter in the matrix of PBT. For the dumbbell bars, all LCP particles develop into long fibrils along filling direction from the converging area of the narrow part and through the entire length of this part (Fig.2a). The formation of long LCP fibrils is attributed to the extension flow in the converging area. However, in the end area of the narrow part, it has been observed that some parts of the matrix resin have been forced to flow perpendicularly to the filling direction and LCP in the matrix is at the same time stretched into fibrils perpendicular to the filling direction (Fig.2b), and the farther the position is from the center, the longer the LCP fibrils were stretched. This phenomenon is obviously caused by the diverging flow at the end of the narrow part. From our previous work, it has been known for these PBT/LCP blends that all LCP domains will be stretched into fibrils when drawing ratio reaches 6 [3]. So, the above results indicate that the extensional ratio of the converging and diverging flow in the dumbbell specimen is at least over 6.

Fig.2 SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of a PBT/LCP80/20 dumbbell specimen
The left drawing is an illustration of the fracture surface position and filling direction

For the square bars, long LCP fibrils closely packed parallel to the filling direction have been observed from the very edge of the specimen to about 60 μm inside (Fig.3a). Further inside into the specimen, both the length and the amount of LCP fibrils decrease (Fig.3b). To about over 100 μm inside, no LCP fibrils but only spherical LCP particles about 1 micron in diameter can be observed (Fig.3c). This result can be explained by the common knowledge that mold filling is mainly a Poiseuille shear flow, while extensional flow occurs along the mold wall. Another phenomenon is that at the end far from the gate, the LCP fibrils seem shorter and less than those near the gate (Fig.3d). These suggest that LCP does not uniformly distribute in PBT matrix and their reinforcing effect can be deduced to change with position. The mechanism of the LCP's non-uniform orientation and distribution need further investigation on the mold filling behaviors of blends.

Fig.3 SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of PBT/LCP80/20 blend square bars. The filling direction is horizontal. a. edge area (near the gate); b. intermediate area; c. core region; d. edge area (far from the gate)

It also has been found in both the dumbbell and square specimens that LCP fibrils are straight at the edge area, which is something like the morphology of continuous fiber composites, but the fibrils become a little zig-zaged in the inside region. It is considered as a result of relaxation of the highly oriented LCP. Another difference of these PBT/LCP blends with other LCP containing blends is that there is no skin-core structures exhibited, although the orientation of LCP is significantly different from the skin to the core region. It may be attributed to the good compatibility between PBT and the PET/PHB type copolyester.

2. MECHANIAL PROPERTIES

Tensile, flexural and impact properties were measured for these blends and compared with those of glass fiber (GF) reinforced PBT. The data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of PBT/LCP blends

	Tensile strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Charpy impact strength (kJ/m ²)	Elongation %
PBT	43.8	1.92	30.2	255
PBT/LCP90/10	51.0	1.90	17.5	17
80/20	52.4	2.05	13.3	1.2
PBT/GF90/10	67.6	4.03	14.8	0.5
LCP	83.0	6.52	26.0	1.0

From these mechanical property data, it can be seen that the tensile strength and flexural modulus are increased with the addition of LCP, but not significantly. The increment of the strength and modulus in these blends, or "in-situ composites", is lower than that of glass fiber reinforced PBT with the same fiber content. In addition, the great cold drawing of PBT is depressed with the addition of LCP, and no macroscopic cold drawing of PBT is observed when LCP content reaches 20 wt-%.

Fig.4 SEM photographs of the tensile fracture surfaces of pure PBT, PBT/LCP90/10 and PBT/GF90/10

Fig.4 shows the tensile fracture surfaces of pure PBT, PBT/LCP90/10 and PBT/GF90/10 observed by SEM. It can be seen that, on microscopic scale, PBT matrix is still largely deformed in the PBT/LCP blends, at least, when LCP content is below 20 wt-%, while the fracture surface of glass fiber reinforced PBT is smooth even at the microscopic scale. This indicates that the LCP fibrils can not bear as much load as glass fiber during the tensile process, which is owing to the fact that the Young' modulus of LCP fibril is much lower than that of glass fiber. For the toughness of the blends, the impact strength and elongation at break decrease with the addition of LCP, which suggest that the toughness is lowered with the addition of LCP, and which is probably due to the lack of interfacial adhesion between PBT and LCP.

CONCLUSION

For the injection molded specimens of these PBT/LCP blends, LCP form fine particles and fibrils with less than 1 micron in diameter in the matrix of PBT. The formation of LCP fibrils was closely related to flow conditions during mold filling, so the length, shape and amount of the LCP fibrils change with the form of the specimen and with position in the same specimen. In dumbbell specimen, LCP forms long fibrils along the filling direction in the narrow part and perpendicular to the filling direction at the diverging end of the narrow part. In square bars, LCP forms long fibrils closely packed and align along the filling direction in the region about 100 μm inside the specimen surface, and spherical domains in further inside region. Tensile strength increase with the addition of LCP, but not as significantly as glass fiber reinforced PBT. The impact properties decrease with the addition of LCP.

REFERENCES

1. D. G. Baird and R. Ramanathan, *Contemp. Top. Polym. Sci.*, **6**(Multiphase Macromol. Syst.), 73-93 (1989)
2. Markku T. Heino, Pirjo T. Hietaoja, Tommi P. Vainio, Jukka V. Seppälä, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **51**, 259-70 (1994)
3. Zhong Yang and Guo Meili, Effect of Drawing on the Morphology and Tensile Properties of PBT/LCP Blends, submitted to *Polymer*